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Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication III

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Abbreviations

LL	Living Lab
NBS	nature-based solutions
KER	key exploitable result
ND	no data available

Background

COEVOLVERS (Coevolutionary approach to unlock the transformative potential of nature-based solutions for more inclusive and resilient societies) **explores how nature-based solutions (NBS) can contribute to the societal change needed to address the biodiversity and climate crisis. The Project works on the co-design of fair NBS governance models, techniques, and practices that are fair for humans and non-humans.**

The NBS approach of the project is embedded in both the human domain of the technosphere (such as urban systems) and the biosphere (such as the corresponding urban ecosystems). NBS combines human elements with natural components and processes, which results in synergetic effects and hence can be considered coevolutionary. Coevolutionary both for the environment made by humans and for nature – such as an urban green space designed to create affordances for humans conducive to a healthy life and for non-humans by sustaining and enriching ecosystem diversity.

The ultimate goal of the project is to provide an understanding of the birth and establishment of fairer NBS, especially from the perspective of the most vulnerable humans and non-humans. For this reason, the project will involve people suffering from loneliness, mental health issues, educational poverty, a lack of green-space-related affordances, climate change, economic isolation due to their rural cross-boundary situation, city dwellers in post-industrial suburbs, and non-humans suffering from urbanization or other aspects of the ecological crisis. The project partners believe that NBS should create a reciprocal relationship between humans and nature.

For COEVOLVERS, it is crucial to explore how nature, the human relation to nature, and NBS are understood and enabled in the everyday lives of citizens. The project examines interactions between the technosphere (green or blue spaces modified and used by humans) and biosphere evolution, spanning from the system level to local interactions between technology, sociocultural structures, and ecosystems.

Some key findings are tested through the seven small-scale pilot projects, the LLs. Seven LLs co-design and apply various tools and methods, and co-develop inclusive NBS and governance models across Europe in different socio-political contexts and with local communities (NGOs, governmental organisations, citizens) including vulnerable and marginalized people and non-humans. The different positions and situations of the participants in the LLs require particular attention in the dissemination and communication activities.

The seven LLs of COEVOLVERS

Introduction

The COEVOLVERS project Strategy and Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC Plan, D6.1), is a tool for helping consortium partners achieve the project’s general goal: “to contribute to the societal change urgently needed to address the ongoing biodiversity and climate crises and to develop a sense of belonging and committed action for nature”. A further aim is “to engage and motivate decision- and policymakers to ensure their contribution to transformational impacts at a local, national, and EU level”. The document referred to above was developed in M6, and this document is the second update. The first update was submitted in M18.

This deliverable has been developed by ESSRG, leader of WP6 (the WP responsible for communication, exploitation, and dissemination), with input from all project partners, as part of Task 6.4 by reflecting on the past 36 months of the project and by reviewing the project's DEC Plan (D6.1) and the update of the DEC Plan (D6.2). WP6 asked all partners to complete a questionnaire (see Annex) and organised and facilitated an online exploitation workshop in M28 to develop the strategic exploitation steps and action plans for exploitation. An in-person communication and dissemination workshop in M35 was also organised to make the first steps for cartoon development and to review our DEC activities of the last 18 months.

This deliverable will be further updated in M48, as D6.4 Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication IV. including the DEC plans for beyond the project lifetime.

The audiences of the project

COEVOLVERS managed to reach many different groups of audiences with tailor-made messages and various forms of communication, dissemination, and engagement activities.

Partners have established both direct and indirect relations from the beginning of the project with

- citizens,
- vulnerable groups at LLs,
- rural communities, including shepherds,
- municipality representatives at the local-level administration,
- policymakers at the local, national, and EU levels,
- researchers (in Europe and overseas),
- landowners,
- garden owners,
- NGOs both in rural and urban areas
- forest managers,
- teachers,
- students (primary and tertiary education),
- tourists,
- and communities of the Overseas Cousins.¹

New audiences were identified and targeted in the last 18 months such as

- the Estonian Folklore Archive network members,
- healthcare professionals,
- healthcare managers and decision makers,
- oncology patients and their families,
- scouts,
- children,
- landscape architects and urban planners
- civil servants working in the municipalities or in public organisations (in Europe and in Shenzhen, China)
- artists from different fields (including writers)
- entrepreneurs/companies (in Europe and in Shenzhen, China)
- rural development agencies.

¹ COEVOLVERS Project is collaborating with three Overseas Cousins by exchanging practical experiences and theoretical approaches to NBS design and implementation. For further information see co-evolvers.eu.

New audiences, oncology patients, for the Italian Living Lab. ©Oriana Mosca

New tools and channels for communication

Some partners have decided on or are planning new communication tools or activities based on their experiences since the project started. Partners also managed to segment their audiences further (see the previous chapter), which will ensure the development of tailor-made communication and dissemination tools and activities.

Living Labs are arenas for raising local awareness and building new types of relations, thus having a central role in communicating and disseminating COEVOLVERS' insights and outcomes. Regarding the new activities of the last 18 months:

The Finnish LL participated at the exhibition at the Nature Forum 2025, and they are preparing an NBS photography contest for the residents of Turku.

The Catalan LL is planning to hold one or two photo exhibitions in libraries in Catalonia.

The Italian LL have recently started to communicate updates on COEVOLVERS-related questions in the University of Cagliari's official web magazine (UNICA Magazine).

The Hungarian LL started to develop the Healing Garden Handbook and participated at exhibitions at various sites to present the research methods they use in the hospital garden.

The Exhibition of the Hungarian Living Lab at the 2nd Congress of Ecological Humanities in Barcelona.
©Beáta Pányta

The Scottish LL has developed a comprehensive NBS benefits guidelines for woodland management through its community-centred approach ([Woodlands for All](#)). The team is actively co-developing a dedicated digital type of virtual commons for Murray Park (<http://murraypark.uk/>), which serves as a central hub for disseminating resources and links for ongoing updates to the broader community.

The LL has pioneered innovative digital engagement tools, including the [Virtual Nature Tool](#) that provides immersive 360-degree experiences of the woodland, particularly enhancing accessibility for individuals with limited mobility. Additionally, they have developed a collaborative Photo App that enables park visitors to

contribute to a user-generated digital archive by documenting their discoveries and experiences, creating a growing repository of visual and textual information about the park's biodiversity and recreational opportunities.

Building on their collaboration experiences, particularly their transformative visit to Peru and partnerships with other LLs, the team is creating digital storytelling content that captures cross-cultural learning and knowledge exchange around NBSs. These narratives highlight the global applicability of their co-evolutionary approach and community engagement methodologies.

To further amplify youth engagement and creative communication, the James Hutton Institute collaborated with students to produce an innovative [LEGO® brick Stop-Motion video](#) that demonstrates NBS concepts in an accessible and engaging format, empowering young people to become storytellers and advocates for NBS.

[LEGO® brick Stop-Motion video](#)

The Czech-Slovak LL is planning an interactive exhibition in cooperation with the Information Centre in Velké Karlovice, in the summer of 2026. The exhibition will be focused on the results of the project for the public, including outputs from digital and art-based methods, such as nature letters, virtual nature tours, and storytelling. The Czech-Slovak LL is also designing a “semi-virtual” educational trail which is based on the distribution of QR codes in landscape with links to nature letters and the platform beskydyonline.eu.

Website and social media

COEVOLVERS uses the project website as one of the main means of external communication, hosted at <http://www.co-evolvers.eu/>. The project website features project-relevant information: objectives, activities, results, outcomes, partners and LLs, news, and events. All partners participate in creating contents for the website.

The social media channels of the project were launched in M9. The [LinkedIn account](#) is the primary social media platform we use. All project partners are encouraged to integrate and repost COEVOLVERS into their communication on LinkedIn.

The use of the [X channel](#) (formerly Twitter) of the project has been reformulated following the changes in the ownership and management of X in the 2023 summer, which have led to a loss of interest in this social media channel by the scientific community (and various other groups of audiences). The loss of audience was

continuing when the owner of X assumed a role in the 2nd Trump Administration from the beginning of 2025. Based on this situation, there's a deviation in the KPI for Twitter in Table 2 (see page 18). Because of the decrease in users, we decided to make LinkedIn the primary social media channel of the project.

COEVOLVERS doesn't have a Facebook account, but several project partners do have one, mostly related to LLs, and they reach several thousand people through that channel.

COEVOLVERS will use the YouTube channel of the consortium leader, LUKE, to publish the LL videos in the last midterm of the project, and the videos can be uploaded to the project partners' YouTube channels as well.

The Zenodo account of the project is managed by WP7. All the EC-accepted deliverables, scientific publications, and general communication materials are available via the following link: https://zenodo.org/communities/coevolvers_2022/

News about the Hungarian LL and the Finnish LL were posted on external Instagram accounts, too.

New tools and channels for dissemination

Most of the partners managed to disseminate the results and learnings generated in the project via new channels and tools. Here are the most important examples:

University of Tartu and the Estonian LL have started partnerships with the Estonian Literature Museum and Folksong Archive, and organised a creative writing workshop focused on urban nature with former Tartu city writer Maarja Pärtna.

The Hungarian LL organised study trips for the hospital staff and National Consultation Group members. The trip to the North Hospital in Vienna, for instance, was a very influential visit where COEVOLVERS' insights could be disseminated and developed.

The Italian LL presented an interactive poster at the bi-annual Congress of the Italian Association of Health Psychology (SIPSA) to disseminate results about a participatory sound mapping activity realized in the LL. Participants of the Congress listened to recorded audios geo-localized in the LL map during the activity with an immersive

audio recording set. The sound recordings were accompanied by descriptions given by the participants of the activity.

Story telling event of the Estonian Living Lab in Tartu, Estonia. ©Lona Päll.

The University of Erfurt contributed to [a policy brief](#) targeting private peatland owners in Finland to assist their restoration efforts, thus supporting the achievement of the EU Nature Restoration Law mandates for peatland restoration. The University of Erfurt also started to collaborate with other projects via the Cooperative Research Centre on Structural Change of Property (Germany) and established connections in Shenzhen, China, by giving in-person lectures at a university, supervising a PhD student exploring NBS in urban areas, and giving interviews in local Chinese media.

Exploitation

The consortium started to work on the detailed exploitation strategy of the project by the end of the first project year, after partners had planned in detail their activities for the project's lifetime and beyond. WP6 started to actively involve partners in the exploitation tasks at the annual project meeting in M18, where an exploitation workshop was organised. The goal of this workshop was to develop a common understanding of exploitation (that is, in line with the Grant Agreement and Regulation 2021/695) and build a list of project results that will be the basis of the key exploitable results and the results ownership list (including the intellectual property rights protection).

Example from a Mentimeter of an exploitation workshop of COEVOLVERS

To reach a common understanding in exploitation, we used the definitions of the European Commission EU&Tenders portal Glossary or Horizon Results Platform as follows:

result²: Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge, and information, whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action, as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights.

exploitable result: Outputs generated during the project, which can create an impact during or after the project lifetime.

key exploitable result (KER)³: An identified main interesting result which has been selected and prioritized due to its high potential to be exploited.

The consortium agreed to follow the following pathway to reach our exploitation goals:

² <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary>

³ <https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-02/HEU%20Results%20platform.pdf>

In M28, another online exploitation workshop was held, entitled “Create a Value Workshop”. The purpose was to discuss the most important selection criteria for identifying the key exploitable results from the potential exploitable results. Participants agreed on the following criteria, which are consistent with the recommendations of the European Commission: degree of innovation, exploitability, and impact.

highest impact (we should choose the actions that has the highest impact on humans and non-humans, the impact should be inclusive); realistic to be implemented; resource driven; degree of innovation; exploitability; applicability (market readiness), timeliness, technology readiness; replicability; context relevance (meaningfulness for people not only researchers; clarity for people who will exploit the result); market need (scope of the potential audience); accessibility for a community; resource driven

Following the workshop, all project partners identified the possible Key Exploitable Results (KERs) of the project and completed a template to report the action plans for each KER, including potential risks that could delay or hinder the exploitation process. Afterwards, each project partner discussed their KERs with their National Consultation Groups. The exploitation action plans are considered living documents, and partners update them as needed.

The KER action plans were reviewed by WP6 and the consortium leader organisation (LUKE) then discussed together with WP5 and WP2. (WP5 is responsible for one of the KERs (Toolkit) and for the task actionable knowledge, which overlaps with KERs,

and WP2, which is also responsible for one of the KERs (Handbook) and at the same time explores the impacts of COEVOLVERS.)

Key exploitable results of COEVOLVERS

	Name of the KER	Responsible partner	Description	Status
1	Handbook	<i>University of Erfurt, LUKE</i>	The Handbook is organised like an encyclopaedia (or "Wiki") and stands out from other materials, such as the toolkit and documents related to COEVOLVERS, by providing a comprehensive overview of the theories, concepts, and methodologies relevant to NBS as multi-species coevolving and cohabitating communities.	under development
2	Toolkit for Nature-based Solutions	<i>James Hutton Institute</i>	A toolkit for more inclusive Nature-Based Solutions combining best practice guidelines, policy frameworks, and stakeholder resources developed through co-evolutionary approaches. The toolkit integrates participatory methodologies, digital tools, and place-based solutions to support transformative governance models across diverse socio-political contexts. Delivered in multimedia formats accessible to communities, policymakers, practitioners, and researchers, it emphasises genuine co-creation and multi-species assemblages. This actionable resource enables the replication and scaling of COEVOLVERS methods for sustainable ecosystem governance and social inclusion.	under development
3	Nature-Based Governance Mode	<i>CETIP, IFE SAS</i>	Nature-Based Governance Mode is an umbrella concept for the transformative governance models (instruments) co-created in COEVOLVERS. These transformative governance modes incorporate human and nonhuman needs and interests for more inclusive, just, and resilient multispecies communities.	under development

Table 1. The list of KERs of COEVOLVERS and their status in September 2025

Responsibility in communication

In relation to the communication process and communication outcomes, all project partners are requested to pay special attention to ensuring that the safety of the groups and communities who participate in LL activities and research is ensured. This includes the participants, the surrounding community, and non-humans.

As some people the project is working with face geographical isolation and economic and social marginalization, COEVOLVERS partners agree that the communication and dissemination activities of the project must be carried out with a caring attitude.

Children's personal data: children merit specific protection on the internet as they are less aware of the risks and the consequences of being present on public platforms. As some LLs are connected to schools and families with children, the consortium agreed to avoid using photos that show children's faces to ensure that children are not recognisable in photos publicly used in our project, even if the parent or the child's legal guardian has signed a GDPR consent form.

Links to other work packages

All DEC activities are supported by the WP6 leader, ESSRG, which not only manages the tasks of WP6 but also provides consultancy and collaboration to all work packages when needed.

WP6 works closely with WP1 and WP5 to ensure strategically planned day-to-day communication, dissemination, and exploitation within the project.

WP1 is responsible for ethical issues and the ethical guide (D1.1), partners consult about ethical dilemmas affecting the communication activities of the project with WP1, who is in contact with COEVOLVERS Ethical Advisor.

WP5 is responsible for exploring the actionable knowledge generated in the project and for translating relevant scientific findings into practical knowledge. WP6 follows this process not only because it provides important communicable messages but also because the work of WP5 strongly supports the exploitation of the project results.

Beside the general communication tools and knowledge, ESSRG provides professional graphic design services to the partners. The materials listed below are

examples of the collaboration of WP6 and project partners to create graphical contents based on the project visual identity.

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⁴ Simo Sarkki, Mia Pihlajamäki, Katriina Soini, Ann Ojala, Tatiana Kluvankova, Martin Spacek, Himansu Mishra, Juha Hiedanpää. 2025. Integrative literature review on co-concepts in connection with nature-based solutions. *Environmental Science & Policy*, Volume 169: 104073. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2025.104073>.

⁵ Published on COEVOLVERS website: <https://co-evolvers.eu/from-linear-promises-of-nature-based-solutions-to-relational-practices-of-nature-based-assemblages-1>

Poster about the Project

Reporting and monitoring

Each partner and LL complete the online Communication Calendar, where they record planned communication and dissemination activities like blog posts, events, presentations, conference papers, local media articles, policy briefs, newsletters, publications, etc.

Partners should report on their DEC activities regularly in an online spreadsheet based on the project's Nextcloud account. The spreadsheet contains information on the type of the event, the number of people reached, and on the different audiences if data is available. Based on this spreadsheet, the KPIs for DEC are being assessed continuously by WP6 and the consortium coordination team.

Until M36 (26 October 2025) the KPIs were accomplished as follows:

DEC measures	KPIs for DEC M1-36	reached numbers
Living Lab videos	700	0
LLs decided to make a video at a later stage of the project when they had a good understanding and knowledge of the LL communities and the changes they could make during the project lifetime and beyond. Most of the LLs started to create their videos in the months preceding the end of the 2nd midterm.		
General video on LLs (views per LL)	500	0
From the 7 LL videos, a general video is going to be edited in the last midterm containing information about all LLs.		
Newsletters (delivered)	500	1132+
Several LLs created newsletters delivered regularly for communication purposes with the community that is interested in their activities and results. Others use their institutional newsletters to add articles about COEVOLVERS-related news.		
Newsletters (participating country)	15	16
COEVOLVERS appeared in newsletters of organisations not related to the project. (e.g., IREAS or other EU-funded projects.)		
Local media articles (per LL)	10	13
LLs do their best to communicate about their activities and engage local people via local media items. However, it seemed a little ambitious to apply this KPI per LL. Realizing this, this reach shows the sum of the appearances in local media of the LLs (including local newspapers, radio shows, and online media platforms).		
News articles (pieces)	20	17
Partners published about COEVOLVERS in thematic newspapers (e.g., forestry magazine) and newspapers covering national and international news, including environmental coverages.		
Peer-reviewed publications (views)	2000	8753+
12 peer-reviewed articles have been published by the project. Their reach is not shown in this number, as not all publishers share their tracking data.		
Website (visits)	1000	4066+
co-evolvers.eu registered more than 3700 visits via the Matomo Analytics service. However, due to privacy policy questions, the website visits were started to be measured only on M23, which means that surely more visits happened than this number shows. 73 articles have been published on the News/Events/Blog subpage since the launch of the website.		
Webpage (visitors)	500	ND
Matomo Analytics is used as website analytics, and it can't register the number of visitors.		
Facebook (group members)	140	8847+

Several partners established Facebook groups for their LL communities or already had one before the project started. It is an important tool for communication of the LLs in terms of reaching people. Project-related communication appeared in other Facebook pages too (e.g.: Estonian National Museum).		
X (Twitter) (followers)	750	56
62 posts have been created since the launch of the account. To understand the deviation, see p.8.		
LinkedIn	100	258
Over 70 posts have been created since the launch of the account.		
Blogs (reads)	500	2664+
Partners published about COEVOLVERS on their own blog pages or on blogs that are not related to any of the project partners. And in M24, a new subpage on COEVOLVERS website was added, the 'Blog' subpage. Partners write posts regularly to this subpage.		
Events (participants)	500	901+
COEVOLVERS participated in both mass events (such as Researchers Night) and small group events organised by the LLs (e.g.sensory walks).		
Annual meetings (participants)	180	220
The project had 4 annual meetings: the kick-off in Turku, the meetings in Budapest, in Cagliari, and in Aberdeen. Besides project partners, advisory board members, and actors from the local communities and the representatives of the Overseas Cousins were invited.		
Presentations (audience)	750	4052+
Project partners presented COEVOLVERS learnings and results at various kinds of events, from university lectures to seminars, scientific conferences, or thematic environmental festivals, and so on. Sometimes, the exact or estimated number of the audience is unknown.		
4 thematic symposiums (participants)	300	210-225+
COEVOLVERS organised symposiums about the most important scientific topics related to the project (eg.in Tartu and Turku) and also organised project-related symposiums at other events (in Barcelona and Vilnius).		

Table 2. KPIs for DEC of COEVOLVERS Project until the 28th October, 2025

Annex

1. History of changes in DEC KPIs

Key results and target groups	DEC measures	KPIs for DEC		Reached numbers		
		M1-18	M1-36	M1-18	M18-36	M1-36
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LL specific tools → Citizens, vulnerable groups at the LLs, local level organized actors and administration 	Videos (views per each 7 LL)	300	700	0	0	0
	Newsletters (delivered)	250	500	440+	692+	1132+
	Local media articles (per LL)	5	10	8	5	13
	Website (visits)	500	1000	1223+	2547+	4066+
	Facebook (group members)	70	140	7818+	8847+	8847+
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusive co-creation practices and tools • improved understanding of marginalisation and vulnerabilities in NBS design and implementation • Typologies for NBS socio-politics implementation and new governance models • Measured nature values and the map of 	General video on LLs (views per LL)	100	500	0	0	-
	Blogs (reads)	200	500	771+	1893+	2 664+
	News articles (pieces)	5	20	8	9	17
	Events (participants)		500	298+	603+	901+
	Policy briefs			-	-	-
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved inclusivity, functionality and effectiveness of NBS → Wider society 	Newsletters (participating country)	8	15	10	6	16
	Webpage (visitors)	200	500	ND	ND	ND
	X (Twitter) (followers)	500	750	65	56	56
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-evolutionary theory and practice of NBS including design principles and methods for NBS, Diagnostic toolkits for NBS design and implementation, and a multimedia toolkit → Research communities 	Linked In	50	100	127	258	258
	Annual meetings (participants)	60	180	133	87	220
	Peer reviewed publications (views)	1000	2000	8753+	ND	8753+
	Presentations (audience)	500	750	2232+	1800+	4052+
	4 thematic symposiums (participants)	100	300	36	189	210-225+
	Handbook (views)			-	-	-

Table 3. KPIs for DEC measures for the 1st and 2nd midterm (until the day of 28th October, 2025).

2. The questionnaire each partner and the Living Lab responded to in M35 Exploitation action plan template

1. Have you discovered any new communication and dissemination tools you are using or will use compared to the tools listed in the previous DEC Plan? (List from the previous DEC Plans: video, local media article, blog post, social media post and channel, policy brief, peer-reviewed publication, symposium, presentation for the researcher community, conference poster, poster exhibition, newsletter, e-mail group, website.)

2. Have you discovered any new audiences you would like to communicate with about COEVOLVERS compared to the audiences listed in the previous DEC Plan? (List from the 1st DEC Plan: Citizens, vulnerable groups at LLs, local-level organised actors and administrations, policy makers at the local, national, and EU levels, wider society, researcher communities. Additions from the 2nd DEC Plan: Hungarian LL - hospital therapists, Slovak-Czech LL - elementary school students.)

3. Is there any new channel that you use or will surely use compared to the channels listed in the previous DEC Plan? Please, check D6.1, pp.12–20 where all public online channels of each partner are listed, and also think of any other channels that are not listed there but you are using or will use during the project lifetime.

4. Are there any new activities you will do other than the activities listed in the previous DEC Plan?

(List from the 1st DEC Plan: Videos, external newsletter entries, local media articles, blogs, news articles, events, policy briefs, peer-reviewed publications, presentations, symposiums, handbook, social media posts. Additions from the 2nd DEC Plan: public events in the LL neighborhood.)

5. During the past year, have you discovered any important issues regarding the vulnerability of the LL group you are working with?

Is there any sensitive information you weren't aware of before starting working with them within COEVOLVERS? If there is, please list them here.